

THE SILVER BIRCH MASTER: A Historiographical Summary of 17th-Century Roman Landscape Attribution

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A. Blunt: "Poussin Studies, V: The Silver Birch Master," *Burl. Mag.*, cxii (1950), pp. 69-73

In this article, Anthony Blunt argues that a group of landscape paintings commonly attributed to Nicolas Poussin or to known followers of Poussin may actually belong to another, unknown follower of the artist. Most of these paintings are similar to landscapes by Poussin in that they "are enlivened with small figures, depicting pastoral, religious, or mythological stories." Yet, Blunt lists several reasons why these works cannot be by Poussin:

They can be clearly distinguished from his works by their far looser spatial construction, the mechanical handling of the trees, and the feebleness of the figures, which, in Poussin's own landscape compositions are always executed with the same care as in his figure paintings.

Although the composition and technique of three of these landscapes recall the work of Gaspard Dughet, they include distinctive foliage and white-striped, birch-like tree bark. These recurrent characteristics lead Blunt to ascribe them to a mysterious painter he calls the "Silver Birch Master."

The author believes that stylistic variations between paintings known to be by Dughet and those he attributes to the Silver Birch Master are indeed by two different hands. For example, most of the trees in early works by Dughet feature heavy, dark-green foliage contrasting strongly against the sky, whereas the Silver Birch Master has painted only a few of his trees in a similar way. Blunt next discusses four more paintings, each with ambitious classical themes. At least one, entitled *Mirtillo and Corisca*, has been connected stylistically with Poussin, and the others with Salvatore Rosa, and all are known from separate locations. As Blunt observes, the distinctive treatment of the foliage in each indicates that all belong to the hand of the Silver Birch Master.

Blunt theorises that, for all these paintings, the Silver Birch Master imitated Dughet's 1640s-era works whilst also borrowing stylistically from Claude Lorraine and Poussin. Nevertheless, the Silver Birch Master was incapable of following Poussin's classical precepts; instead he "invented a softened version of it." In this way, the Silver Birch Master popularised Poussin's somewhat severe manner, making it accessible to a broader audience. Additionally, Blunt describes Dughet as one of the most distinctive imitators of

Poussin's landscape style in the school of Poussin-inspired painters. This school, which includes the Silver Birch Master, remains shrouded in academic uncertainty.

L. Salerno: Landscape Painters of the Seventeenth Century in Rome (Rome 1977-8), ii, nos 86.1-86.3

Salerno here discusses the landscape paintings of Gaspard Dughet in terms of the three distinct stylistic phases first identified by Pascoli and Pio, and which can best be understood in the context of the artist's relation to Nicolas Poussin. Whilst Salerno recognises Dughet's landscapes as primarily Italianate, the author also acknowledges the important influence of Northern painters in the development of his style.

According to Salerno, the first of Dughet's three artistic periods is a so-called "youthful phase" beginning in the late 1630s. Around this time, Dughet participated in the execution of the famous cycle of landscapes for the Cason del Buen Retiro in Madrid along with Poussin, Lemaire, Swanevelt, and Jan Both. As Salerno also observes:

To this youthful phase belongs a group of paintings assembled some time ago by Blunt under the name of a hypothetical "Silver Birch Master," the name being taken from a type of tree that is frequently found in the various paintings in this group. Later, by common agreement, the painter was identified as the young Dughet.

Salerno agrees with both Pascoli and Pio in describing Dughet's manner during this youthful phase as "drier" in comparison to his later works. These early paintings are predominated by scenes of the hunt and of everyday life, some including figures executed in the typical fashion of the Bamboccianti.

Inspired by Poussin's "classical and architectonic landscapes" such as *Pyramus and Thisbe*, Salerno believes Dughet's work became "characterised by 'greater simplicity, greater verisimilitude and more learning.'" This "language of the classical ideal" defines Dughet's second phase beginning around 1650. During this period, compositions such as the *Storm* became more unified as the artist lent an underlying structure to his naturalistic scenery. Dughet's third and final phase, from around 1660 on, bears stylistic similarities to the late Romantic landscapes of Poussin and to Salvator Rosa's "more picturesque style." Indeed, as Salerno points out, works by Dughet are frequently misattributed. The source of the confusion is twofold: one is the absence of a catalogue raisonné, and the other is the problem of inaccessibility, since many of Dughet's works remain in private hands.

C. Whitfield: "Poussin's Early Landscapes," *Burl. Mag.*, cxxi (1979), pp. 10-19

Clovis Whitfield's thesis is that the progressive elimination of decorative landscapes from the canon of Nicolas Poussin by the scholars Blunt, Friedlaender Magne, Grautoff, and Thuillier has limited our understanding of Poussin's development. Indeed, Poussin is generally considered the greatest landscape painter of the seventeenth century. According to Whitfield, this is despite the fact that Poussin is known as such only within the context of his more philosophically profound mature

works. Here, the author hopes to rectify this error by “restoring to [Poussin’s] authorship some of the pictures still attributed to him as late as the nineteenth century.” His goal is to discern “a more even progression towards the great landscapes of the 1640s, to see the parallels that there are between Poussin’s attitudes to this kind of work and those of his immediate contemporaries, and above all to comprehend his dedication to the study of Nature.”

To this end, Whitfield sets his sights on a group of paintings attributed by Sir Anthony Blunt to an artist descriptively dubbed by the latter as the “Silver Birch Master.” Although several of the works in this same group had at one time been credited to Poussin, since the publication of Blunt’s article in 1950 “this distinctive hand has come to be thought of . . . as that of the young Gaspard Dughet.” Still, Whitfield disagrees. He believes that they are, in fact, by Poussin.

Firstly, Whitfield argues that Poussin, during his early studies, must have produced drawings from nature depicting a variety of subject-matter. All of these would have been relevant to a decorative style of landscape painting. The author cites the then-recently-cleaned and well-preserved *Venus and Adonis*, lent by the Musée Fabre at Montpellier, as evidence of the artist’s early landscape style. According to Whitfield, an inscription on the verso of this work links it with near certainty to Poussin.

Next, Whitfield mentions the fact that several pen-and-wash drawings, all of which resemble the early-1630s style of both Claude and Poussin, had been rejected as such by Blunt, Walter Friedlaender, and John Shearman. The author acknowledges the difficulty in attributing these works to Poussin, since they cannot be associated with particular paintings. Nonetheless, Whitfield believes that a group of eighteen such drawings, which Shearman had earlier attributed to Dughet, has “an extremely good claim to be by Poussin.” Whitfield reasons that, whilst the sensitivity of technique used in these drawings is uncharacteristic of Dughet, it does bear a close resemblance to the stylistic qualities found in Poussin’s *Venus and Adonis*. It also echoes those in paintings attributed by Blunt to the Silver Birch Master.

Landscape with St. Jerome, for example, had traditionally been the only canvas attributed to Poussin in a series of decorative landscapes painted for the Cason del Buen Retiro in Madrid. In 1950, however, Blunt had recognised this canvas amongst a dozen others as having actually been produced by the hand of the so-called Silver Birch Master. Whitfield here disagrees with Blunt, believing that all of these paintings “do indeed belong together, but as the work of Nicolas Poussin himself.” The author continues:

There is indeed no difficulty in recognising [Poussin’s] hand in the St. Jerome, for not only the figure but also the landscape itself indicated his brushwork, and they are closely linked with the landscapes of the early 1640s. The complexity of the composition, with patches of light used as much as the differentiation of the trees in indicating the recession, is fully Poussin’s own, and echoes similar features in the drawings.

According to Whitfield, another painting from the Buen Retiro series, as well as two smaller landscapes with animals (one in the National Gallery, London, and the other in the Salting Collection), reveal these same stylistic features. They are therefore consistent with the hand of Poussin. Moreover, in re-attributing Blunt’s thirteen Silver-Birch-Master-paintings to Poussin, Whitfield uses the details of chubby, short-

winged putti and other small mythological figures inhabiting them. The author states that the aim of his argument is to “reinststate attributions that in most cases were current until Magne, Grautoff or Friedlaender, and to find a place in Poussin’s career for the study of nature that is such a self-evident ingredient in his art.”

A. Blunt: “Letter to the Editor: The Silver Birch Master, Nicolas Poussin, Gaspard Dughet and Others,” *Burl. Mag.*, cxxii (1980), pp. 577-82

Anthony Blunt’s letter concerns an article by Clovis Whitfield published in a previous edition of the *Burlington Magazine* (January 1979, pp. 9-10). Here, Blunt agrees with Whitfield’s suggestion that early landscape paintings by Nicolas Poussin, Poussin’s brother-in-law Gaspard Dughet, and a mysterious artist known simply as the “Silver Birch Master,” should be open to reconsideration. Nevertheless, Blunt takes issue with Whitfield’s sweeping re-attribution of thirteen paintings and several drawings to Poussin. Where both Blunt and Professor John Shearman had previously ascribed the drawings to Dughet, the paintings had been credited to the Silver Birch Master by Blunt himself.

Blunt points out that it was he who had “invented” the Silver Birch Master in association with these paintings. However, in responding to Whitfield’s suggestion that they belong instead to the hand of Poussin, Blunt admits that some do contain “tangible points of comparison with ... certain works of Nicolas.” Still, a few of the paintings “fit in perfectly with the relatively mature Gaspard” and have nothing in common with Poussin. According to Blunt, the only way Whitfield could have ascribed them all to Poussin is because he had never actually seen them. Blunt refers to several illustrations in refuting Whitfield’s attributions. One of Blunt’s examples is *Landscape with a Cowherd*, a painting in the National Gallery, London, which has traditionally been ascribed to the Silver Birch Master. The canvas does contain figures and architecture similar to those in works by Poussin, but the looser handling of these elements aligns it stylistically with the influence of Dughet.

Blunt concedes that he is no longer entirely confident that the drawings in question are by the hand of Dughet. Still, he “cannot believe that they are all by Nicolas.” Whilst Blunt observes that the subtle shading and details of foliage in drawings such as *Landscape with trees* in the Musée Cantini at Marseilles were probably beyond the ability of Dughet, still they are closer in “spirit” to Claude than Poussin.